

ROLE OF LIBRARY ASSOCIATIONS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF LIBRARIES AND ITS PROFESSIONALS IN INDIA: AN ANALYTICAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

In the modern Society, Library is the brain of an institution. For the development of libraries, Library Associations have been established which play a vital role for the cooperation among libraries and its professionals. The basic assignment of a library Association is to improve, expand and the professional knowledge in the library and information institutions and research centers, to provide leadership quality among the library professions, promote and improvement of library services, to promote educational programs and other innovative programs and publications. This study covers the total span of all level Library Associations in the arena of library and its profession.

KEYWORDS: Library Association, ILA, IASLIC, Librarianship, Library Personnel

INTRODUCTION:

The contemporary LIS Profession is changing and increasing its scenario through the rapid development of latest technology. Library Association is the cornerstone by which the structure of library movement can be erected. It plays a crucial role for the development of its library and librarianship as a good profession. The first Library Association was established in 1876 named as American Library Association in USA and the second was library Association of Great Britain. The library development of a country depends upon its Library Associations. Indian Library Association (ILA) was established on 22nd September, 1933 in Calcutta. It is the largest and renewed Library Professional body in the field of Library and Information Science in India. There are some other Library Associations are also there in India like IASLIC, CGLA, IATLIS, MALA and DLA for the conveying useful messages, guidelines for library development, helping them exchange opinions and promoting free access to information and improvement of library activities smoothly.

OBJECTIVE:

The most important objectives of this paper are as follow

1. There should be a mutual co-operation among the Library professionals and there Associations for the smooth development and effective functioning of library.
2. To help libraries and provide effective services to students, research scholar and faculty at larger.
3. To support the cause and development in the field of library profession.
4. To know how much they are active in playing in LIS education by organizing seminar, conference, workshop and other training program etc.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY:

There are many library association has been established from earlier to nowadays at different levels i.e. national, state and regional levels in different group that is academic, public and special library associations. If we collect the data about their role and regulation for the development of libraries and their professionalism exhaustively, we should study their publications at a glance, but it is time consuming and very difficult task. This study is done by collecting data from the websites of some renewed library associational all over the India.

LIBRARY ASSOCIATIONS IN INDIA:

There are large number of Library Associations have been established for their development of libraries and its professionals in India. Some are mentioned below.

Sl. No	Library Associations	Year	Place
1.	Andhra Desa Library Association	1914	Andhra Pradesh
2.	Maharashtra Library Association	1921	Maharashtra
3.	Bengal Library Association	1925	West Bengal
4.	Baroda State Library Association	1926	Gujrat
5.	Madras Library Association	1928	Madras
6.	Karnataka Library Association	1929	Karnataka
7.	Punjab Library Association	1929	Punjab
8.	Indian Library Associations(ILA)	1933	New Delhi
9.	Government of India Library Association(GILA)	1933	Delhi
10	Bombay State Library Association	1935	Bombay
11	Bihar Library Association	1936	Bihar
12	Malabar Library Association	1937	Kerala
13	Assam Library Association	1938	Assam
14	Utkal Library Association	1944	Orissa
15	Travancore Library Association	1945	Travancore
16	Kerala Library Association	1945	Kerala

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17	Hyderabad Library Association	1951	Hyderabad
18	Uttar Pradesh Library Association	1951	U.P
19	Delhi Library Association	1953	Delhi
20	Gujarat Library Association	1953	Gujarat
21	Indian Association of Special Libraries and Information Centers(IASLIC)	1955	West Bengal
22	Madhya Pradesh Library Association	1957	Madhya Pradesh
23	Rajasthan library Association	1962	Rajasthan
24	Academic of Library Science and Documentation	1965	Hyderabad
25	Jammu & Kashmir Library Association	1966	Jammu & Kashmir
26	Haryana Library Association	1966	Haryana
27	Tripura Library Association	1967	Tripura
28	Indian Association of Teachers of Library & Information Science(IATLIS)	1969	Hyderabad
29	Bombay Science Librarians Association	1975	Bombay
30	Medical Library Association of India	1981	New Delhi
31	Indian Theological Library Association	1985	Maharashtra
32	Manipur Library Association	1987	Manipur
33	Mizoram Library Association	1987	Mizoram
34	Meghalaya Library Association	1994	Meghalaya
35	Nagaland Library Association	1996	Nagaland
36	Society for Advancement of Library & Information Science	2002	Tamilnadu
37	Central Government Library Association	2004	Uttarakhand
38	Jharkhand Information and Library Association	2007	Jharkhand

Beside these library associations, there are also several other library associations like school library association, college library association, district library association, village library association etc.

ROLE OF LIB. ASSOCIATIONS FOR DEVELOPMENT OF LIBRARIES AND ITS PROFESSIONALS.

In attempting to answer the question presented by the title of this paper, we have omitted many associations and mainly focused only on two associations and these are as below:

1. Indian Library Association (ILA):

In the year 1933 happens to be the most significant year in the history library and information science in India. A library association was established on 13th September, 1933 i.e. Indian Library Association was formally formed at the 1st All India Library Conference held at Calcutta. A.C.Woolner was the first chairman of ILA. It is the largest and eminent professional body in the field of library and information science in India. The membership of this association is more than 7000 all over the India. The head quarter of ILA has been shifted from Calcutta to Delhi in August, 1964.

ILA was established to provide a wide verity of library services and cause of library movement and development in India. The objectives of the associations are mentioned below:

1. Promotion of library movement all over the India.
2. Development and Improvement of library science education and provide training program to the library science professionals.
3. Improvement of library services in all its aspects in India.
4. Promotion of research in the field of LIS and co-operation with international organizations.
5. Increase more publication of periodicals, newsletters, books etc are the main source for the development libraries by ILA.
7. Promotion of library legislation in India.

ILA is a permanent member of International Federation of Library Associations (IFLA) & Common wealth library Association (COMLA) which organized International Federation of Library Associations conference in 1992 in New Delhi. The first and foremost activities of Indian Library Association (ILA) organization of workshops, seminars, convention, training programs in a university or an institution and other activities which can promote and improvement libraries, research centers and its professionals in India. Some other activities also performed by ILA includes library legislation, library cooperation, resource sharing, collection development, national pay policy, library networks, library research and library educational development of academic, special and public libraries all over the India.

ILA published ILA Newsletter every month and other important publications are the proceeding of All India Library Conference from 1978 to till date, India library directory, A survey of public library services in India and year's work on Indian librarianship.

Indian Association of Special Libraries and Information Centre (IASLIC)

IASLIC is a non-profit making national professional body was established on 3rd September, 1955 at the lecture hall of Indian museum, Calcutta by J.Saha, A.K.Mukherjee and G.B.Ghosh. Dr. S. L Hora was the first president and J. Saha was the first General Secretary of IASLIC. Which promote and support for the overall development of special libraries and its professionals in India, The following objectives of IASLIC are as below:-

1. To act as center of research and studies in special libraries.
2. Organize meetings, workshops, seminars and conference all over the India.
3. Promote the publications of journals, newsletters, conference proceedings and reports.
4. To promote the quality of library and information services.
5. Conduct the short term training course for the improvement of technical efficiency of library professionals.
6. Collaborate with other professional bodies in promoting the interests of the LIS professionals.

The major function of a library association is the promotion and development of professionalism and standards of libraries. IASLIC has been organized Workshops, seminars, and conferences all over the India which are usually arranged by University libraries, Research centre, Educational institutions and organizations, department of library and information science etc. The association also involve in other activities like training programmes, study circles for knowledge and skill development of professionals and publications of periodicals. IASLIC provided a training program entitled; "Training in Special Librarianship and Documentations" form 1964 to 1963and also conducted some foreign language courses in German, French and Russia. IASLIC is affiliated with IFLA and FID and plays an important role for the international cooperation of the two federations.

It published IASLIC Bulletins, IASLIC Newsletter, and Indian Library Science Abstract (ILSA), Monographs, Conference/Seminar volumes and Digitized IASLIC publications.

FINDING:

The finding of the study revealed that the impact of enhancement library professionals and the libraries in India. In the above analysis, we can find that so many associations are established in all over the India. All are playing a major role for the development of libraries and their professionals. Among the associations ILS and IASLIC are taking part a vital role for the betterment of librarianship for conducting workshops, seminars, conferences and some relevant educational and training programmes, research programmes in every year in India but reason is that the development and improvement in the field of library and its professionals is very less. Not only ILA or IASLIC is responsible but also other associations are responsible for the present poor condition of librarianship in India. This is the reason that after 72 years of independent, what is the proper development of public libraries in India? All associations just give their comments on problem but not take against necessary actions to solve the problems. More than 85% states have already passed library act but not functioning

properly. As such the development of the nation through library services is neglected in some states and its services beyond the reach of the rural poor.

CONCLUSION:

LIS associations plays an indispensable place for the growth and progress of library and its professionalism. Almost in every place of the country so many reputed organizations are their libraries are there but the professionals are not getting adequate facilities like social and professional's status, proper training, research activities and proper salaries and respect. Therefore library associations should endeavor for development of library services and improve the status and condition of services of library personnel all over the India

REFERENCES:

1. Satpathi, J.N., Satpathi, Chitra and Ghosh, Gurudas(2012), " Role of IASLIC in Developing Computer Skills Among LIS Professionals in India " *Bangladesh Journal of Library and Information Science* Vol-02, No-01(July, 2012):39-47. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3329/bjlis.v2i1.12917>
2. Rai, Additya Kumar.(2017), " Role of Library Associations in the Betterment of Librarianship in India." *Library Waves* Vol-03, No-01(Jan-June, 2017): 68-73.
3. Ghosh, Maitrayee.(2006)," The emerging role of national and regional associations in library development: an Indian perspective." *Library Review* Vol. 55 No.-1(2006): 45-58, DOI 10.1108/0024253061064178.
4. Ossai-Ugbah, Ngozi Blessing.(2013), " The Role of Professional Library Associations and Institutions in Facilitating Access to Information in Africa." *Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies* Vol-2, No- 2(July, 2013):263-270, DOI: 10.5901/ajis.2013.v2n2p263.
5. Kuri, Ramesh and Palled, Savita(2016), " Bibliometrics Study of Journal of Indian Library Association (ILA)." *International Journal of Digital Library Services* Vol-06, Issue-01(Jan-March, 2016): 49-57
6. Swain, D. K., (2011), *Library Philosophy and Practice, 2004-2009: A Scientometric appraisal*. *Library Philosophy and Practice*; Available in <http://unllib.unl.edu/LPP/>
7. Gupta, S. (2013). Library profession at cross roads: challenges before library associations in India. *Library Herald*, 51(4), 289. doi:10.5958/j.0976-2469.51.4.006.
8. Gupta, S. R. (2013). Library profession at cross roads : challanges before library associations in India. In *Prof. P N Kaula Memorial Lecture* (pp. 1–14).
9. Vinayagamoorthy, P., Singh, N., & Kumari, D. (2015). Role of library associations to promote education, research and training. *Remarking*, 1(9), 10–15.
10. <https://www.ilaindia.net/>
